

INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING A FOCUS ON 3D PRINTING METAL

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ABSTRACT

The paper provides an overview of additive manufacturing and its widespread applications in various industries. The primary objective of the paper is to gain a deeper understanding of additive manufacturing processes and highlight the benefits it offers to essential industries in our modern world. The research primarily focuses on the utilization of 3D printing technology for metal fabrication, which holds significant importance in numerous major sectors. Among these sectors, aerospace has emerged as a prominent industry that extensively leverages 3D printing technology.

The research findings indicate that the additive manufacturing industry has witnessed substantial growth in recent years, driven by its cost-effectiveness. Projections suggest that the industry could experience a remarkable annual growth rate of up to 27% across all sectors, paving the way for a promising future.

INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing process has evolved with the advent of 3D printing, allowing for the creation of items that were traditionally made using different methods. While plastic models are the most common objects printed using 3D printers, their accessibility has increased significantly due to lower costs, making them more accessible to the general public.

In industrial applications, 3D printers utilize various materials. For instance, in construction, large-scale 3D printers use a cement mixture to create entire house walls, highlighting their capacity for printing on a larger scale. In the field of medicine, there are ongoing developments in additive manufacturing of organic tissue. Another crucial material for additive manufacturing is metal, which requires a different process called metal sintering. This process involves adding layers of metal dust and using a laser to harden the material until the desired product is achieved. To print a specific item, a 3D model must be created first. 3D modeling has become an indispensable skill in almost every industry, as product development in the modern world heavily relies on this technology. Looking ahead, the future of 3D printing is expected to bring bigger, faster, and more affordable printers. It will continue to become increasingly accessible and could even find applications in household tasks.

This research aims to address the following research questions:

- Which industries have embraced additive manufacturing to the greatest extent?
- Which countries are leading in the utilization of additive manufacturing?
- Will 3D printers become more affordable in the future?

3D PRINTERS

While 3D printing has been around for decades, it has surged in popularity and usage in recent years. New 3D printing applications are constantly being developed, making it one of the fastest ways to make prototypes, including those with complex geometry. Much of the reason for the recent upswing in 3D printing use is that it is a simple technology that can be used in applications in all fields. In its early years, 3D printing presented high entry costs. 3D printer models and materials were expensive. In recent years, with improvements and variations in the technologies of both the machines and materials used, prices have decreased, making 3D printing applications more accessible and cost-effective across industries and education. (Smith, 2022)

Additive manufacturing, often known as 3D printing, is gaining popularity among manufacturers. The demand is increasing as a result of the revolutionary benefits it offers. Industrial 3D printing is a viable production solution that allows you to reimagine your product from the ground up by incorporating design for additive manufacturing. Due to the design possibilities offered by additive manufacturing and industrial 3D printers, you may optimize your product, increase efficiency and quality, and reduce expenses. (Smith, 2022)

Many companies are currently using industrial 3D printing as one of their key resources. Demanding industries such as automotive, medical, architecture, and luxury, as well as drones and robotics, are leveraging this revolutionary technology to satisfy the needs of their projects! This technology's adaptability and materials will provide numerous benefits to any organization, allowing it to meet new difficulties. (Smith, 2022)

INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION OF 3D PRINTING

1. Prototyping

Prototype development is the first and by far the largest application of 3D printing technology. In the early days of 3D printing, designers and engineers recognized they could save time and money by printing rather than machining prototypes. In recent years, however, printer costs have decreased substantially, while output quality has grown to the point that even inexpensive printers can produce prototype-quality parts. (Smith, 2022).

The prototyping value of 3D printing was estimated at \$4.4 billion in 2020. (Errera, 2023)

- 2. Mechanical engineering.** The industry is taking steps to rectify this situation by installing its own 3D printers to shake off the shackles of its suppliers' schedules. 3D printers can supply high quality versions of parts such as clamping fixtures. A first wave of companies is also starting to print its own consumables, such as milling tools and drill bits, asserting their independence in this area, too. More and more machine makers are discovering new functionalities through 3D printing – for instance nozzles that can be hugely improved by simply modifying the shape of the channel. (Kaliudis, 2022)
- 3. Healthcare and dentistry.** Using human tissue and cells as material, healthcare professionals are now ready to 3D print skin, body parts, and organs with functional cells with a particular person's anatomical structure – leaving less room for rejection. Medical discoveries in bioprinting, reproduction, and prostheses are possible by 3D printing. There are numerous medical developments to which 3D printing contributes. (Smith, 2022)

These sectors are also playing a pioneering role, with 3D printing proving to be particularly popular for items such as dental prostheses, inlays and other implants. In practice, you need both off-the-shelf and custom-built parts, because every hip and dental prosthesis is different. Custom implants are easier to insert and can help patients recover faster. One likely development is that imaging methods will be used to measure a patient's knee or jaw and then send a CAD blueprint of the required implant directly to the 3D printer, which will then immediately start building it. (Kaliudis, 2022)

- 4. Aerospace.** The aerospace industry was the first to embrace 3D printing, and now regards it as a standard part of their toolkit. The reasons are: unlike cars, aircraft are in almost constant use and spend very little time parked. That means the price of each individual component plays much less of a role. The decisive factor is how well it fulfils its intended use – and in this case lightweight design is the name of the game. If you can make an aircraft component one kilo lighter by modifying its design,

- that can translate into direct savings of hundreds of thousands of euros in kerosene costs over the aircraft's service life. (Kaliudis, 2022)
5. **Construction.** Construction 3D printing provides a variety of technologies that rely on 3D printing as the primary method for creating buildings or construction components. Molding (concrete/cement, wax, foam, and polymers), powder bonding (polymer bond, reactive bond, sintering), and additive welding are 3D printing applications used in construction. In the construction industry, 3D printing has numerous applications in the private, commercial, industrial, and public sectors. (Smith, 2022)
 6. **Automotive.** Audi has utilized 3D printing for a considerable amount of time and has no plans to stop. Similar to the aerospace industry, the automotive industry has a strong interest in the capacity to print complicated and infrequently used lightweight components on demand and at a cheap cost. The automotive industry can use 3D printing for engines, body parts, and chassis, and in the future may be able to 3D print entire cars significantly faster than in present production periods. (Smith, 2022)

THE 3D PRINTING INDUSTRY STATISTICS

- The global 3D printing market reached a value of \$13.8 billion in 2021.
- The value of the North American 3D printing market in 2021 was \$5.72 billion.
- Various analysts predict that the 3D printing industry will grow at staggering speeds – between 18% and 27% per year.
- About 2.2 million 3D printer units were shipped in 2021.
- Equipment costs more: The 3D printing equipment market was valued at \$4.5 billion in 2021, while the materials market was \$1.7 billion.
- The most profitable 3D printer manufacturers are AutoDesk, HP Inc., 3D Systems, Desktop Metal, and Proto Labs. The market value of AutoDesk is above \$68.2 billion.
- Investors understand the trend: back in 2018, VC funding for 3D printing start-ups surpassed \$300 million.
- Companies that already utilize 3D are hooked too: over 23% reported investing more than \$100K into 3D printing tech in 2020.
- When asked about the benefits 3D printing has over other production methods, 69% of respondents say they use it for its outstanding ability to create complex geometrical objects, 52% value the quick iteration of products, and 41% claim its mass customization abilities are important.
- Out of companies that utilize 3D printing technologies, 38% consider it their main activity, while another 18% have in-house departments dedicated to it, and 16% use 3D print across multiple departments (Errera, 2023)

THE LEADING COUNTRIES THAT HAVE APPLIED ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING IN THEIR BUSINESSES

South Korea is known to be ahead of the competition in terms of already applying additive in companies from different industries, followed closely by China and Canada. Europe is represented closely after with France, the UK and Germany. (figure 1)

Figure 1: n=900 companies, EY global 3DP survey, 2019

Source: 3D Printing Statistics, 2023

The 3D printing software segment is smaller than the hardware and materials segments. However, in recent years it's been on a steady growth path, driven by the need to overcome multiple challenges within the 3D printing workflow. (40+ 3D printing industry stats you should know, 2021).

Today's 3D printing software solutions are unlocking the possibility to create complex designs faster and increase print success rates. In addition to that, ensuring part quality and managing workflows more efficiently have also become possible with the development of a new generation of software products. (40+ 3D printing industry stats you should know, 2021)

Figure 2: the software segment was relatively small in 2018, but it holds huge potential to grow into almost a billion worth of opportunity within the next decade

Source: 40+ 3D Printing Industry Stats You Should Know, 2021

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING IN CONSTRUCTION

Additive manufacturing in construction is closely linked to the type of material that is being printed. The method used to create the building part is dependent on the material used, with concrete, metals, or polymers (plastics) being the most common. With aggregate-based materials like concrete, the material is generally extruded into layers of the desired shape. Alternatively, a particle-bed process is used where the dry materials are layered and then the fluid added afterwards to bond the materials together. Other types of additive manufacturing include dynamic casting and mesh molding for concrete, while metal parts use techniques such as powder bed fusion and directed energy deposition where a heat source fuses the metal together. Plastics – as one of the most adaptable materials – have a wide range of methods that can be used for additive manufacturing, dependent on the type of polymer used. (Additive Manufacturing in Construction, 2020)

The Benefits of Additive Manufacturing for Construction: Traditional construction processes such as bricklaying and concrete reinforcement installation are time-consuming, labor-intensive, and come with risks to the safety of the workforce. They also limit the designer to the forms and structural strength that can be achieved with traditional building components. In contrast, additive manufacturing offers greater design freedom (figure 3), improves workplace safety and productivity, and lowers production costs. Not only can virtually any shape be produced, objects can be created with varying materials to increase the strength of any areas of the object that will be subject to high loads. This provides designers with new options for optimization of the components. In addition, the automation that additive manufacturing offers makes it particularly suited to construction projects in harsh environments, such as areas affected by atomic radiation. (Additive Manufacturing in Construction, 2020).

Figure 3: a render of a 3D printed house created with much more design freedom than a traditional house

Source: *How 3D Printing Has Transformed the Construction Industry, 2018.*

The main components of an Additive Manufacturing machine are the six-axis robotic arm, which moves the concrete nozzle used for printing; the concrete mixer and concrete pump, which feed the concrete to the nozzle; and the robotic arm control unit (figure 4). (Additive Manufacturing in Construction, 2020).

Figure 4: The generic components of a 3D printer used in construction.

Source: *Additive Manufacturing in the Construction Industry: The Comparative Competitiveness of 3D Concrete Printing, 2021.*

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING IN MEDICINE AND DENTISTRY

The advantage of additive manufacturing comes from creating complex structures that vary in complexity, customization, lightweight, strength, and speed. As additive manufacturing for medical devices continues to gain momentum, there are five main areas where we are seeing the most growth opportunity from this evolving technology (Williams, 2022).

Dentistry

Many 3D-printed dental appliances are easily customized for a precise fit while also being printable in a variety of substrates, from flexible polymers (figure 5) to rigid titanium. There are also specialized printers configured to use the dental scanning software, along with biocompatible resins, that can fit in small offices and clinics for immediate, on-the-spot solutions ready in a single day (Williams, 2022).

Figure 5: 3D printed teeth customized for a precise fit

Source: *Why is dental additive manufacturing growing? 2019*

Medicine

3D printing is firmly established in the highly innovative medical industry, which to this day makes up one of the largest markets in the additive manufacturing sector, second only to aerospace. The list of possible applications is long, including 3D printed drugs, prosthetics, implants, surgical tools, and of course medical models. (3D Printed Medical Models – State of the Art 2022, 2022)

Although models have been used in medical care for centuries, patient-specific medical models generated from patient scans and confirmed by trained medical professionals bring a wide range of advantages over traditional models or 3D imagery, such as:

- Better insight into patient-specific anatomy (figure 6)
- Better medical diagnosis
- Better pre-operative planning resulting in shorter surgery time
- Simulation-based surgical training and education
- Development of patient-specific surgical guides and tools
- Development of patient-specific implants
- Better patient counseling and education (3D Printed Medical Models – State of the Art 2022, 2022)

For everything from rare tumors to cardiac models incorporating complex blood-flow fluid dynamics, life-size and extremely accurate 3D printed medical models improve the quality and safety of surgical procedures by enabling physicians to plan and even practice various approaches, as well as size or pre-fit medical equipment. Time saved in the operating room reduces the likelihood of additional procedures, and has been shown to improve post-operative outcomes and lower the duration of patient hospital stays. (3D Printed Medical Models – State of the Art 2022, 2022)

Figure 6: Models to help medical professionals as well as patients better understand medical procedures

Source: 3D Printed Medical Models – State of the Art, 2022

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

In the automotive industry, OEMs have historically mostly used additive manufacturing for rapid prototyping. In more recent years however, advances in additive manufacturing (AM) have slowly been transforming the ways in which end-use parts are designed, manufactured and distributed (figure 7). Deloitte's 3D opportunity in the automotive industry study explains that in the current standard AM path, companies do not seek radical alterations in either supply chains or products. AM is adopted to create design iterations, to enhance quality through cost-effective prototyping, and to create specific tooling parts. Nevertheless, other AM paths in automotive exist, which transform products and supply chains more radically. This is what we will explore in the following overview of additive's impact in the automotive industry. In fact, SmarTech Analysis' report revealed that by 2029, automotive 3D printing will have generated \$9 billion in revenue from the production of end-use parts alone, compared to \$1.39 billion in 2019. (Martel, 2021)

AM also means greater personalization possibilities. In fact, some luxury car makers already use AM to deliver designs specialized to customer requirements. Traditional manufacturing methods such as CNC or injection molding wouldn't be able to deliver unique parts under competitive lead times. The cost of producing such parts would also be considerably different. Moreover, personalization can also be used to deliver spare parts, to repair an older car model for example. (Martel, 2021)

Figure 7: Autodesk's generative design tools helped design lighter wheels on a Volkswagen 1962 Type 2 11-window Microbus

Source: *The Role of AM in the Automotive Industry, 2021*

Figure 8: Ford's 3D printed aluminium inlet manifold | Photo Credits: Ford

Source: *The Role of AM in the Automotive Industry, 2021*

One example of an end-use case application is Ford's 3D printed aluminium inlet manifold (part of the engine that supplies the fuel/air mixture to the cylinders) (figure 8), which was installed in a 1977 Hoonitruck. According to the manufacturer, this replacement part was the largest automotive 3D printed part ever produced. It took five days to print using the Concept Laser X LINE 2000R from GE Additive. Historically, Ford is one of the companies that has conducted the most research in AM industrialisation. In 1986, it had already invested in an SLA 3 (the first 3D printer ever made). The company stated in an official press release: "It didn't take long to see that the invention could be used to create new

prototype part designs faster and more efficiently than ever.” Today, the company has printed over 500,000 parts and “saved billions of dollars and millions of hours of work.” In its Advanced Manufacturing Centre in Detroit, it has invested in FDM, SLS and sand 3D printers. (Martel, 2021)

METAL ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

Metal Additive Manufacturing, also known as Metal 3D Printing, is a technology used to produce three-dimensional parts formed layer by layer by using a metal powder that is melted with a laser source. (Additive Manufacturing Solutions, 2022)

Advantages of Metal Additive Manufacturing:

1. Design freedom

Thanks to its layer-by-layer creation process first and foremost, metal additive manufacturing provides freedom of design that is unthinkable with traditional metalworking technologies. By 3D printing a component rather than machining it, you can produce complex geometries with unmatched accuracy and detail. In this way, you can redesign components with a shape that is functional to their use rather than a shape that suits the production technology. What's more, you can consolidate multiple parts into one piece, resulting in a better-performing design while eliminating assembly time and related issues. With additive manufacturing, you can also make parts with very complex internal channels, which ensure optimal cooling of the components.

(Discover how Additive Manufacturing can revolutionise your business, 2022)

Figure 9: an example of an optimised design to reduce the weight of a manufactured part

Source: *Discover how Additive Manufacturing can revolutionise your business, 2022*

2. Lighter parts

Since component design is optimised according to its actual use, you can create lighter parts by emptying full parts into lattice structures, creating organic, fluid shapes where previously there were square, solid parts (figure 9). Think of the advantages that lighter parts can bring to sectors such as aerospace or motorsport: greater competitiveness, better performance in cars, reduced fuel consumption in aircraft, etc. (Discover how Additive Manufacturing can revolutionise your business, 2022)

3. Rapid prototyping

An object can be designed, printed, and tested much more quickly and accurately, eliminating several steps in the product development process, with a drastic reduction in errors, thanks to a system that controls the whole production process layer by layer. In this way, the lead time from idea to the final product is shortened, prototyping time is reduced and this allows you to go to market faster, as well as to test more variants and customisations. This offers your customers better and more reliable parts, improving the whole product development process. (Discover how Additive Manufacturing can revolutionise your business, 2022)

4. Reducing waste

With the layer-by-layer powder fusion process, only the material needed to produce the object is used. The metal powder used in the production process and that is not melted can be recycled and used later. This drastically reduces production waste, which is a major issue with traditional machining technologies. (Discover how Additive Manufacturing can revolutionise your business, 2022)

5. More product control

The infinite possibilities offered by additive manufacturing allow you to make any part that can fit within the working area of the machine. In so doing you can produce parts that were previously made by different suppliers, or make third-party parts for the most varied of sectors. In addition, additive manufacturing revolutionises the supply chain: it is, therefore, possible to produce parts on-demand, preventing large stocks of spare parts being kept in a warehouse, but producing only what is needed, when it is needed, avoiding long waits and transport costs. (About Additive Manufacturing, 2022)

Powder Bed Fusion solutions

With Powder Bed Fusion technology, you can make objects having very complex geometries, with internal channels or very small parts, thus giving the finished piece a truly functional design. (About Additive Manufacturing, 2022)

The Powder Bed Fusion process includes the following commonly used printing techniques: Direct metal laser sintering (DMLS), Electron beam melting (EBM), Selective heat sintering (SHS), Selective laser melting (SLM) and Selective laser sintering (SLS). (About Additive Manufacturing, 2022)

Powder Bed Fusion – Step by Step (figure 10):

1. A layer, typically 0.1mm thick of material is spread over the build platform.
2. A laser fuses the first layer or first cross section of the model.

3. A new layer of powder is spread across the previous layer using a roller.
4. Further layers or cross sections are fused and added.
5. The process repeats until the entire model is created. Loose, unfused powder remains in position but is removed during post processing. (About Additive Manufacturing, 2022)

Figure 10: Power Bed Fusion Process

Source: About Additive Manufacturing, Powder Bed Fusion, 2022.

Pros and Cons:

Advantages:

- Relatively inexpensive
- Suitable for visual models and prototypes
- (SHS) Ability to integrate technology into small scale, office sized machine
- Powder acts as an integrated support structure
- Large range of material options

Disadvantages:

- Relatively slow speed (SHS)
- Lack of structural properties in materials
- Size limitations
- High power usage
- Finish is dependent on powder grain size (About Additive Manufacturing, 2022)

METAL SINTERING

What is metal sintering?

To make small metal parts, you've got to poke them, prod them, and (usually) put some heat to them. Metal is stubborn, and sintering helps make sure the powder behaves after your part is formed. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

The sintering process in powder metallurgy (PM) (figure 11) involves heating a compacted powder to fuse the particles, which leads to a harder, stronger part. While the compaction process does a lot of the work, the physical pressure produced in the press isn't enough to create a final, work-ready component. Sintering is what comes after – the final major step to produce a powder metal part you can rely on. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

Figure 11: Metal sintering process and components.

Source: (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

1. Choosing a Powder Composition

After talking with you about your performance requirements, your manufacturer will pick a powder composition that will yield the right results. The powder mix will include the basic stuff you need, such as iron, nickel, molybdenum and or copper. It will also include other substances like lubricants to improve the flow of the powder into the die. Lubricants are removed by evaporation and heat as a leadup to sintering in a single-furnace process. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

2. Compaction

After the powder is poured into the die, it's pressed with a whole lot of force to interlock the powder. The pressure creates connections strong enough to be called "green strength." A green part won't exactly crumble in your hands, but it still needs to be finished by sintering to achieve optimal strength and hardness. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

3. Sintering

Sintering is done by putting your parts through a rather toasty furnace. The goal is to control the temperature so it reaches just below the melting point of your parts' primary metal ... but not quite. The sintering process causes the metal particles to bond together so you get a part that does what you need it to do. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

SINTERING VS. MELTING

It's easy to assume they're very similar, but there are distinct differences between sintering and melting. Melting actually gets the metal hot enough that it changes from solid to liquid. Sintering is different because the heating process is highly controlled. You get the enhanced properties you need without having to melt the metal. One of the great things about sintering is that you can easily make parts out of metals with high melting points. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

Sintering can accomplish a lot when done right, including:

- Eliminating the lubricants in the compacted powder
- Reducing the amount of oxygen on the powder's surface
- Developing sintered necks between the particles, reducing pores and increasing strength
- Partially or fully diffusing other elements in the mix, such as nickel, copper, and graphite

The last two points are of key importance to the customer. These steps are what produce better properties for your part. (What is Sintered Metal, 2020)

ANSWERED RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Which industries have embraced additive manufacturing to the greatest extent?

The mechanical engineering industry holds the largest market share in the field of 3D printing, with a recorded market worth of \$12.6 billion USD in 2020. It is projected to grow significantly, reaching \$34.8 billion USD by 2026, reflecting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 22.5% (Kaliudis, 2021).

The industry of prototyping comes in second place, with a valuation of \$4.4 billion USD in 2020. Following closely is the aerospace industry, which recorded a value of over \$2.66 billion USD in 2021. The medical industry also demonstrates a substantial investment in 3D printing technology, estimated at approximately \$2.4 billion USD for the acquisition of 3D printing appliances (Kaliudis, 2021).

2. Which countries are leading in the utilization of additive manufacturing?

According to the 40+ 3D Printing Industry Stats You Should Know (2021), the leading countries in terms of utilizing additive manufacturing are as follows:

- South Korea
- China
- Canada
- France
- UK
- Japan
- Germany
- USA

However, the 3D Printing Sentiment Index 2021, as discussed in the Dig Deeper into 3D Printing Sentiment (2023) report, reveals different results in terms of sentiment towards 3D printing. The index scores for selected countries are as follows:

- US: Index score of 160.3
- UK: Index score of 145.5
- Germany: Index score of 123.8
- France: Index score of 115.7
- China: Index score of 114.2
- Mexico: Index score of 113.4
- Japan: Index score of 100.0
- Switzerland: Index score of 99.4

These scores reflect the sentiment and attitudes towards 3D printing in each respective country, indicating variations in perceptions and acceptance of the technology.

3. Will 3D printers become more affordable in the future?

The field of 3D printing is poised for significant growth, characterized by advancements in size, speed, and cost-effectiveness. Rapid progress is being made in 3D printing technologies, driving the expansion of options available in terms of specialized materials that possess the desired properties for end-use parts. This development is propelled by the increasing demand for such materials. For the new generation of printers, particularly industrial-grade solutions, the ability to handle a broader range of advanced materials will be crucial. This advancement paves the way for businesses to leverage additive manufacturing in areas that were previously inaccessible (Váradi, 2022).

While it may be premature to label 3D printing as a mature technology, it can be likened to its teenage years. Over the past decade, 3D printers have experienced a decrease in price, enhanced user-friendliness in setup and operation, and improved reliability. Moreover, the cost of entry may be lower than anticipated, as many features that were once exclusive to high-end models have made their way into affordable alternatives (Hoffman, 2023).

CONCLUSION

Additive manufacturing has emerged as a pivotal enabler for the advancement of various industries in recent years. It is regarded as one of the most influential inventions for sectors such as aerospace, automotive, and medical.

The incorporation of additive manufacturing in these industries offers several advantages. One notable benefit is the cost reduction achieved through optimized designs that minimize material usage. This not only drives economic efficiency but also contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing pollution. Additionally, additive manufacturing has played a significant role in addressing poverty. The ability to rapidly print houses provides quick and accessible housing solutions for the underprivileged. Furthermore, the fields of medicine and dentistry have made remarkable progress, facilitated by additive manufacturing, enabling advancements that would otherwise be unattainable.

Regarding global implementation, Asia stands as a prominent region in terms of 3D printing adoption, closely followed by European countries and the United States.

The future of additive manufacturing appears highly promising. Speculations indicate that it will witness unprecedented growth in funding and advancements in hardware and software development. Moreover, it is expected to become more affordable and accessible, driving its widespread adoption and application.

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